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Experiences on Educational Support Services of International Online Filipino Students: A Narrative Inquiry

Signor Rinno D. Montales,* Luningning B. De Castro, Luzale D. Henson, Ronnie G. Cainglet,
Niclie L. Tiratira, Ligaya Z. Del Rosario, Vivian I. Buhain
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

Online education has expanded globally in secondary schools, offering flexibility, affordability, and access to diverse courses. This study aimed to explore the experiences, motivations, challenges, and suggestions of international online Filipino students regarding educational support services. A narrative inquiry approach was employed, interviewing seven international Filipino online learners residing in various countries. The study utilized the 3-dimensional space approach to craft the re-storying of the participants' narratives. Thematic analysis uncovered emergent themes in participants' experiences with educational support services, providing a deep understanding of their online learning journeys. A total of twelve themes encapsulated the many-sided nature of online learning experiences. The participants shared diverse narratives, revealing personal motivations for choosing online learning and their experiences with educational services. They appreciated the accessibility of online resources but faced challenges such as difficulties in the learning environment and motivational obstacles. Valuable recommendations were provided, emphasizing personalized assistance and flexible scheduling. Ongoing adaptation and innovation of online platforms were deemed crucial to meeting students' evolving needs. Understanding the narratives of international online Filipino students and addressing their recommendations could create more inclusive and effective online learning environments. This study contributes insights into online education, informing the development of tailored support mechanisms for diverse student populations. By addressing the unique experiences and needs of international online Filipino students, educators and policymakers could enhance the accessibility and effectiveness of online learning platforms on a global scale.

Keywords: *educational support services, narrative inquiry, international students, online learning, experiences*

Introduction

The rise of online education has become a significant development in the global educational landscape, especially accelerated by the COVID-19 pandemic. This shift has created a new learning community: online learners. As educational institutions worldwide adapt to this modality, the importance of providing effective educational support services has become increasingly evident. These services, which include academic counseling, online tutoring, and access to digital resources, are vital for helping students achieve their academic goals in an online setting. Despite the growing prevalence of online education, there remains a gap in understanding how international students, particularly Filipino online learners residing abroad, experience and utilize these support services.

This research aimed to explore the narratives of international Filipino senior high school students enrolled in online programs at New Era University Integrated School. By examining the experiences of students from diverse countries such as Japan, Saudi Arabia, and Thailand, this study sought to understand their motivations for choosing online education, the challenges they encountered, and the educational support services they accessed. The research also aimed to gather their recommendations for improving these services. The study's findings highlight the unique needs of this student population and the critical role that tailored support services play in their academic success.

In this article, we report on the findings of this narrative inquiry, which provides valuable insights into the online learning experiences of international Filipino students. We discuss the challenges they face, the effectiveness of the current support services, and propose recommendations for enhancing these services to better meet the needs of online learners in similar contexts.

Research Questions

The purpose of this narrative inquiry design was to explore the diverse narratives of international Filipino online learners residing abroad regarding educational support services, which were a type of service focused primarily on meeting the academic needs of students and supporting their learning and educational goals, provided by the New Era University Integrated School. The overarching problem addressed was to gain a comprehensive understanding of the narrative portraits, challenges, and recommendations of these students in their online learning journey. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following research questions:

1. What were the narrative portraits of international online Filipino students?
2. Why did the participants choose to be online learners?
3. What educational services did the participants experience as online learners?
4. What were the challenges faced by online students that necessitated educational support services?
5. What suggestions were made to enhance the educational support services provided to online learners based on the gathered

narrative of the study?

Literature Review

Online Learning

Online learning, also referred to as distance learning or e-learning, is a method of delivering resources and instruction over the Internet. It enables students to enroll in courses and earn degrees without having to physically visit a campus, and it can be a useful and practical option for them because it allows them to learn at their own pace (Asad et al., 2023).

Online education has several benefits, including flexibility, affordability, and access to a greater course. Online learning is flexible because it enables students to follow the schedule, learn at their own speed, and finish or submit tasks whenever it is convenient for them. By eliminating the allocations for transportation and relocation expenses, the cost is reduced. Students can enroll in courses through online learning from any location. Spending as much time as necessary on each session is possible since online learning allows for pacing flexibility. Moreover, this method of learning enables real-time, interactive instruction via video chat and messaging, and the students are guided by the teacher during online classes (Bozkurt & Sharina, 2020).

When face-to-face instruction is not feasible due to emergencies like COVID-19 and other health issues, typhoons, floods, and other natural calamities, political and social issues or conflicts, and the like, students are given the option of continuing their education through online or e-learning. During the outbreak of Pandemic COVID-19, online learning became a popular method of instruction (Hawley, 2021; Wang et al., 2021).

Three main challenges--technological, pedagogical, and social--were identified by one of the studies on the difficulties of online learning (Ferri et al., 2020; Adnan, 2020). The technological challenges are the unreliable Internet connections and a lack of basic electronic gadgets among many students. The pedagogical challenges include the lack of digital skills among teachers and students, the absence of structured content despite the abundance of online resources, the lack of interactivity and motivation among students, and the teachers' lack of social and cognitive presence to sustain communication within the community of inquiry. Finally, the social challenges are the lack of human interaction between teachers and learners, as well as the latter group's lack of classrooms at home and the lack of parental support when parents are usually remotely in the same locations.

While there are certain drawbacks to online learning and teaching, it is still the method of choice for continuing education under difficult conditions (Ferri et al., 2020). At present, since the COVID-19 Pandemic and its effects are regulated and manageable, most learning institutions have returned to the traditional method of teaching and learning. However, many schools still use or have incorporated online, or, in some cases, a blended format that combines both in-person and online teachings and learnings (Wang et al., 2021).

Nolasco (2022), in his study conducted in the Philippines on online or remote schooling, suggested that planning and preparation are essential to avoid issues or problems in conducting online teaching and learning. It is important for the administration, teachers, and students to be prepared. Assessments are also required to determine what needs to be prioritized or addressed during the operation of online schooling. Additionally, the school administration must pinpoint particular areas within the educational system that requires development. Furthermore, online teachers and online learners need to be properly oriented to using the online applications or resources.

Online Learners

Online learners exhibited diverse characteristics that were influenced by a range of factors, including demographics, prior educational experiences, learning preferences, and technological proficiency. These parameters, including those that were mentioned in the succeeding paragraphs, contribute to the unique profiles of online learners, shaping their motivations, engagement levels, and learning outcomes in online learning environments. Understanding the multifaceted nature of online learners' characteristics were essential for educators and instructional designers to tailor online learning experiences effectively and support the diverse educational needs of learners in digital contexts.

Students in online learning were expected to enjoy flexibility in learning, focus on their choices, experienced asynchronous activities and felt connections with their peers and teachers while conducting online classes (Ames, 2020)

Main (2023) mentioned that online learners often have greater autonomy and flexibility but exercising self-regulation. It is the process by which students actively participate in their own education by using a variety of self-regulated learning techniques to keep an eye on the manage their motivation, cognition, and behavior while being guided and restrained by their objectives and the surrounding context. Online learners need to manage their time effectively, as they have the responsibility to set their schedule. Online learners set specific, measurable, and achievable goals for their online studies. They are intrinsically motivated to succeed, thus adept at monitoring their own progress. Online learners can adapt to different formats, technologies, and instructional methods. They are resilient to overcome setbacks, persist in the face of challenges, and maintain a positive attitude toward their studies. The relationship between self-regulated online learners and educational support services is crucial to fostering a positive and effective online learning environment. Educational support services are designed to assist learners in various aspects of their academic journey, and self-regulated learners can benefit

significantly from these services: access to resources, study skills development, technology assistance, peer and tutoring support, and academic counseling and advising, to name a few.

Cebi et al. (2022) studied how the characteristics of learners influence their behavior when studying online. With the use of sequential pattern mining and clustering approaches, the study revealed that the cognitive traits of learners revealed notable variations. The variations were demonstrated between 74 undergraduate students from a public university in Brazil and four different types of learning materials in an online learning environment. Online learning platforms give students unrestricted access to instructional materials and the ability to log their interactions with the materials throughout use. It is feasible to analyze learning behavior and identify navigating patterns through the learning contents by using data mining techniques to the student log data of those systems.

Ammigan (2019) discovered that certain online learners have specialized demands, such as need for financial stability. These students anticipated that attending school via online education will improve their educational experiences without spending much and that they will get support services to address any emotional or psychological issues that may arise as a result of any form of transition difficulties.

When it comes to online learners confidence and readiness, Martin et al. (2020) found that there were substantial changes in students' views of online learning competencies depending on the race (white and nonwhite) and course style (asynchronous, synchronous, and blended), as determined by Multivariate Analysis of Variance (MANOVA). This survey study looked at how prepared students were for online in 2018 using two metrics: the students' confidence and the priority they placed on online learning. The study employed repeated measure analyses of variance to investigate variations in the participants' perceptions of importance and confidence. Time management, technological competencies, and qualities of online students were graded. Significant priority in relation to communication skills. When it came to time management and communication, students felt more secure about their technical skills and traits as online learners.

A study on the factors influencing the success and completion of online courses was carried out by Soffer & Cohen in 2019. Using learning analytics, a comparable paradigm was applied to four online courses with a total enrollment of 646. According to the study, participating in different activities with course materials and reading forums predicts achievement in the final exam, while completing learning activities and turning in assignments predicts completion of the course. Additionally, students that were actively involved in their academic work had a high degree of learning outcomes. Put another way, it was discovered that there was a 12 substantial correlation between academic achievement and active participation in online courses.

Giray et al. (2022) carried out a local study regarding the online learning experiences of Filipino college students. 71 Filipinos participated in the study, which was done during the COVID-19 Pandemic, when most schools worldwide adopted online learning to continue educating the students. A qualitative approach was used to classify themes from the data that was gathered. The findings demonstrated that while online learning offered beneficial opportunities for learning during the pandemic, most students found it challenging especially when it came to acclimating to this method of instruction. In addition, issues with the internet access, mental health, expenses, time, and space management were present. A great deal of the participants pursue their education because of their worry of being left behind.

The Namibia University of Science and Technology (NUST) included eight regional centers that were used to identify difficulties faced and ascertained students' requirements. According to the research, most students chose distance learning because it enabled them to balance employment and school. Due to their high failure and repeat rates many of them required more time to earn certifications, This may be attributed to a lack of resources and students' underused of them; a lack of cooperation between tutors and lecturers; and a lack of participation by both students and tutors and lecturers in tutorial classes (Shikulo & Lekhetho, 2020).

The characteristics of online learners, influenced by their behavior, shaped the landscape for educational support services. Recognizing and addressing these characteristics allows support services to be more responsive, personalized, and effective in meeting the unique needs of individual learners in the online learning environment. By tailoring support services to the diverse characteristics of online learners, educational institutions can enhance student success and satisfaction in online education.

Experiences of Filipino Students Abroad

This part presents the related studies to elucidate the characteristics and demographics of Filipinos residing abroad, laying the groundwork for a deeper understanding of their experiences and support needs in face-to-face and/or online learning environment.

Chung (2023) investigated the variables influencing students' motivation for online learning through cross-cultural research in the Philippines and the United States. The emphasis of the study was on American and Filipino students' technical and psychological views and how these perceptions affect their goal orientation for online learning. Online learning was impacted by disparate cultural perspectives and IT infrastructure levels, according to the study Every relationship held significance for both nations. But for American respondents, external regulation has no effect on intrinsic motivation, whereas for Filipino respondents, an external reward has a detrimental impact on intrinsic motivation. This study indicated that for both American and Filipino students, the intention to take online classes was influenced by psychological and technological aspects.

An article by Guison (2022) that appeared in the online daily Rappler+ shared the narrations of two Filipino exchange students who were studying and living overseas: a 27-year-old Filipina in Louisiana, USA, and a 24-year-old Filipino studying in Pisa, Italy. The

main motivation for going abroad as an exchange student was to build a strong CV that would impress potential employers and increase their chances of landing a job. Studying overseas exposes one to new ideas and methods of learning. The drawbacks include increased costs, loneliness from feeling so far away from home, and adjusting to new cultures and languages. In spite of all of this, the exchange program is still, hands down, the greatest way to learn outside of the country.

An article written by Montemayor (2023) and published by Philippine News Agency online discussed the challenges faced by Filipino students recruited to study abroad, leading to unmet expectations and academic failure due to misinformation. The President of the IDP Education Philippines noted the difficulties in tracking Filipino students overseas who struggle to achieve their academic goals, citing issues such as course mismatch, difficulty adjusting to climate and culture differences, and lack of effective study habits. Despite these challenges, the report highlighted that 53,000 Filipino students are currently studying in the top five destination countries - Canada, Australia, the UK, New Zealand, and Ireland - with the market growing at a rate of 8 to 13 percent annually. Many of these students are pursuing postgraduate studies.

Support Services for International Students

Some research about the vast array of support services that must be provided or were provided or experienced by international students, whether they were enrolled in traditional classroom setting or online, is featured in the paragraphs that follow.

Hawley et al. (2019) asked 644 students enrolled in higher education to report their pandemic-related concerns and to understand the support services that must be provided by different educational institutions across seven countries - the USA, the Netherlands, Ireland, South Korea, China, Malaysia and Taiwan. These students reported their major concerns. They are in areas of education, safety, mental health, employment stability and finances, uncertainty about the future, and relationships. Minor concerns include economy, politics, travel, and inaccurate data. Possible solutions for these issues include improved or increased communication, participatory research, and expanding students services to include full virtual or online access. The key services identified in the study are technical aid, social support, career planning and placement, and mental health intervention.

Martirosyan et al. (2019) found out that six main categories of services offered at universities were identified and described to gain a deeper understanding of the types of student support programs that might be most helpful in facilitating international students' social adjustments and academic success while studying in the United States. The list included programs for English language learners, academic (educational) support and student performance, special writing aids, social and cultural events, professional development seminars, and family programs. They provided a range of specific initiatives to aid students with their social adjustment, academic performances, and language development to increase the retention and involvement of international students before the start of the pandemic.

Educational Support Services for Online Learners

The following paragraphs are some studies, reviews, and published reports on educational support services for online learners. It became apparent that, although substantial research existed on the topic of educational or academic support services provided to students of face-to-face and online schooling, no direct study or literature had been written about the educational support needs and services provided for Filipino students pursuing online education while residing abroad.

Educational support services can be limited to enhancing academic achievement and learning satisfaction. He et al. (2019) studied the ways in which online schools enhance learning results, boost satisfaction among students, and offer learner support services. In this study, the influence of educational support services on course retention, learning outcomes, and student satisfaction has been examined. Academic support is covered by an online learning support service. Two online learning support (OLS) services and their effects on student engagement were used to investigate the link between these services and students' involvement in the long-term learning process. The two OLS services used visual analytics tools and learning log data to examine how students interacted with an online course. The results showed that the pattern and degree of students involvement were closely correlated with the usage of services and the frequency of use, which implied that the use of OLS services may be included in the list of indicators that represented students' learning status.

In recent years, educational or academic support services for online learners have included technical support, ensuring students and teachers received assistance with technical issues related to online platforms, softwares, and hardware for smooth access to course materials and learning resources. Online learning can provide students with experiences like teaching them how to use the internet for informational purposes. Students can connect with professionals and other students to share ideas, accessing a multitude of global knowledge made possible by the internet (Yuhanna et.al., 2020). Additionally, online study groups or discussion forums were available for collaboration, discussion of course material, and sharing resources with peers. Interactive learning tools were integrated into the online course platform to enhance engagement and comprehension.

Another educational support service provided for online learners was online tutoring, which was offered through virtual sessions or platforms. This allowed students to receive one-on-one support from subject matter experts or peer tutors. In Rajabalee and Santally (2020), tutor support emerged as a significant factor influencing the satisfaction levels of online learners, with some students expressing negative emotions due to insufficient tutor assistance. Additionally, the study emphasized the importance of online learners'

contentment and engagement as crucial aspects defining their educational experiences. Despite ultimately performing well, an analysis of student comments revealed frustration stemming from technological issues and a lack of tutor support. Promptly recording these feelings during module presentation was essential for addressing online learners' concerns effectively. This period coincided with educational institutions transitioning to e-learning to ensure service continuity, leading to significant policy implications for online learners' experiences.

Virtual advising services, which offered educational or academic support remotely by video conferencing, email, or chat, to help with course selection, degree planning, and academic progress, were another educational service offered to online learners. In the study by Bilquise et al. (2023), the elements influencing university students' behavioral intents to adopt an academic advising chatbot were investigated. The findings showed that behavioral intention for chatbot adoption was highly influenced by perceived ease of use and social influence, but not by perceived usefulness, autonomy, or trust. Moreover, the research offered suggestions on how educational institutions may use AI-powered chatbots for academic assistance.

Online library services, which provided access to digital resources such as e-books, academic journals, and research databases, along with virtual reference services and research assistance, are essential for online learners. Writing centers also offered online support for writings assignments, grammar, citation styles, and academic writing skills. In Martzpukou's (2020) conceptual paper, academic libraries were highlighted for their renewed mission to support learners in the online or digital realm, helping them become both information-rich and digitally competent. The paper emphasized the opportunity for academic libraries to serve as a connecting link to advance a strategic vision that prioritized equity in education.

Online seminars and webinars provided educational support to online students by covering subjects including time management, study techniques, and test preparation, aiming to enhance academic achievement. Pedroso (2021) conducted a research to summarize the knowledge gained by students through participating in webinars. Six participants were selected for the study using purposive sampling based on inclusion criteria, and a qualitative-narrative analytic approach was employed. Through participating in webinars, students gained knowledge on various topics, including straightforward yet profound explanations, modest but sincere emotions, impartial yet compassionate assessment, fragmented but comprehensive study, creative but individual conclusions, and firm but purposeful actions. Moreover, the study revealed that webinars were found to be a practical and adaptable tool for teaching and learning. Accepting webinars as an additional and substitute source of information and abilities can make teaching and learning more efficient, enjoyable, and valuable.

A study by Keerthirathne (2020) outlined the peer learning method included in the western approach, based on psychological and sociological theories, educationists developed peer learning as a teaching and learning strategy. Online learners were paired with mentors or peers who had experience to offer assistance and guidance through mentoring programs. Groups of people who connected with one another shared a similar status engaged in peer learning. The findings of the study supported the provision of peer mentoring as another educational support service offered to online learners. The study conducted a literary survey, analyzing books on peer learning, pertinent research articles, and conference papers as secondary sources. Content analysis was employed as the research method, assessing related data in relation to the content analysis method.

Rotar (2022) carried out a comprehensive analysis of the 28 empirical studies on successful interventions and support tactics that the SCOPUS database had indexed between 2010 and 2020. According to the analysis, the timing of when support was provided affects how successful it was. Additionally, it was found out there was still a lack of study in two areas related to support delivery: the support at transitions and the measurements of support interventions. Ultimately, the analysis revealed two new trends in the support of assistance of online learners. The first was the growing influence of technology followed by the use of social media platforms to create support interventions and second was a move toward a more individualized but all-encompassing approach to student assistance.

Research Methods Used to Study Educational Services

An investigation via case study was conducted among Chinese nurses who spent a year earning a graduate nursing degree in the United States (Wolf & Phung, 2019). They were using English as a medium of instruction. The participants' perceptions of social, linguistic, and academic difficulties were examined, as well as coping mechanisms and academic support programs intended to assist students succeed in their studies. Three points in time were used to collect survey data, and each participant had three interviews. The study revealed that participants struggled with academic writing, speaking experiences, the use of moderate-to-high levels of strategies, and the available educational support services. In conclusion, the educational or academic support services provided by the university, consideration by faculty, the kindness and patience of the professors, staff, and local students, and a supportive peer network are likely important in promoting international students' positive experience and success (Wolf & Phung, 2019).

In Malaysia, between May 16 and June 5, 2020, which was the initial peak of the pandemic, a study was carried out by Al-Kumaim et al. (2021), using an exploratory qualitative research technique. This study had two major objectives. One is to examine whether university students' usage of online learning platforms during the COVID-19 Pandemic offered any learning obstacles. The second was to create a conceptual model to lessen the effects of such difficulties. The stated difficulties include (a) the work and information overload from the instructors; (b) the inadaptability and unfamiliarity of the new online learning environment; and (c) difficulties with stress and anxiety-related issues in one's own personal health. A conceptual-motivational model for long-term and healthy online

learning was created from this study.

In the article published by Azzhrawi (2021), he discussed the critical role of narrative inquiry and how to engage in this design ethically and honorably. He mentioned that engaging in this design posed several research issues. One of them was that it is not an easy task to reflect and articulate another's voice; it needs to be done with reverence and modesty. The researcher should adhere through dialog and critical consciousness and through an intersubjective lens to the principles of respect, beneficence, and justice to ensure that the research supports the participant and facilitates their transformation to achieve empowerment.

In a recent study, 15 Asian international undergraduate students who had taken online courses from the United States universities were studied utilizing narrative inquiry, conducted with Cong (2023). The purpose of the study was to better understand the distinct experiences of these learners. The results showed that these online learners have a variety of interconnected identities. The study was also carried out in order to give educators insights on how to facilitate and design online courses effectively. Moreover, the study also emphasized how factors that affect learners' online learning performances include learner autonomy, course design, the atmosphere of the online learning community, and the learning process and experience.

While previous studies have examined the broader landscape of online learning and support services available to learners, none have focused explicitly on the experiences of Filipino senior students navigating virtual education in an international setting. As such, this research addressed the limitations of existing studies by exploring the unique challenges faced by Filipino students studying online abroad and identifying strategies to enhance the provision of educational support services for this population. This dissertation aimed to contribute to the future development of educational support services that are necessary and beneficial for international Filipino online students.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a qualitative research methodology rooted in the principles of interpretivism, aiming to understand social phenomena through the lived experiences of participants (Johnson & Christensen, 2016). Qualitative methods were particularly suited to exploring the subjective perspectives of international online Filipino students, providing a deep understanding of their interactions with educational support services. The narrative inquiry approach was chosen to capture the rich, multifaceted stories of these students, emphasizing their personal experiences and the meanings they attributed to their educational journeys.

The qualitative design of the study was guided by constructivist and interpretivism paradigms, which recognize the subjective nature of reality and the importance of individuals' interpretations. Narrative inquiry allowed for a flexible exploration of participants' stories, prioritizing their voices and ensuring that their experiences guided the research process. Reflexivity played a crucial role, with the researcher maintaining awareness of personal biases and ensuring that the research was conducted transparently and ethically (Nyirenda et al., 2020). This design fostered a collaborative and participatory approach, inviting students to actively engage in meaning-making, which ultimately generated valuable insights into their online learning experiences.

Respondents

The research was conducted within the virtual learning environment of New Era University Integrated School, located in Barangay New Era, Quezon City, Philippines. This institution provides a comprehensive online education program for students from pre-grade school to senior high school levels, making it an ideal setting for exploring the experiences of international online Filipino students. The study focused on the educational support services available in this online setting, including academic advising, access to learning resources, and feedback mechanisms, which were critical to understanding the challenges and successes of the students.

Through narrative inquiry interviews conducted via video conferencing, participants were encouraged to share their stories and perspectives, offering insights into their interactions with educational support services. This virtual setting provided a rich context for exploring the unique needs of international online learners, and the data collected from these narratives contributed to a deeper understanding of how educational support services impact their academic success.

The study's sample comprised seven senior high school students enrolled in the online programs of New Era University Integrated School. These participants were selected through a purposive sampling approach, focusing on specific criteria: enrollment status, geographical location, age range, and experience with online learning. The students, aged 16 to 18, were all Filipino nationals residing in various countries, reflecting a diverse range of backgrounds. They had been enrolled in online classes for a minimum of three years, ensuring they had sufficient experience to provide valuable insights into their interactions with educational support services.

The sampling process began with the distribution of a demographic questionnaire to all eligible students, which helped identify those who met the study's criteria. From an initial pool of respondents, the sample was narrowed down to seven participants, with an additional participant included for trial purposes. Although the sample size was relatively small, the narrative inquiry design prioritized the depth and richness of the participants' stories over the quantity of respondents. This approach ensured that the study achieved theoretical saturation, where no new themes emerged, thereby enhancing the validity and comprehensiveness of the findings.

Instrument

Data were collected through a combination of semi-structured interviews, video recordings, personal narratives, messaging platforms, and visual artifacts. Semi-structured interviews, conducted via Google Meet, provided in-depth insights into the participants' experiences with educational support services. These interviews were video-recorded to capture non-verbal cues and enhance the depth of the analysis. The recordings were transcribed and validated through consultation with participants, ensuring the accuracy and credibility of the data.

In addition to interviews, participants were asked to write personal narratives, offering a supplementary source of data that allowed them to express experiences they might not have shared verbally. Messaging platforms like Telegram and Messenger facilitated real-time, asynchronous communication, overcoming geographical barriers and enabling continuous dialogue between the researcher and participants. These platforms fostered rapport and trust, encouraging open and honest sharing of experiences.

Visual artifacts, such as pictures submitted by the participants, played a crucial role in adding depth to the research findings. These images provided additional context to the participants' online learning environments, complementing the textual narratives and offering a more comprehensive understanding of their experiences. The integration of these diverse data collection methods enriched the study, providing a nuanced and holistic view of the challenges and successes faced by international online Filipino students in their educational journeys.

Data Analysis

This study utilized Lebov's Framework (Lebov, 1972, as cited in UK Essays, 2018, and Parks, 2023) to explore the experiences of international online Filipino students with educational support services, focusing on identifying their needs, challenges, and aspirations in the online learning environment. The data analysis began with the transcription of interviews, personal narratives, and online messages, followed by an initial reading to gain a foundational understanding of participants' experiences. Key themes and insights were noted during this process for further exploration.

The re-storying process then organized participant narratives to address the research questions, integrating a three-dimensional space approach. This approach considered how the participants' experiences evolved over time, highlighting key events, transitions, and the influence of physical, social, and virtual spaces. Additionally, it examined how cultural, social, and personal factors shaped the participants' subjective viewpoints, providing a comprehensive understanding of their experiences with educational support services. The data were then systematically coded using open, axial, and selective coding, which led to the identification of significant themes. Finally, the researcher reflected on these findings, considering their broader implications for theory, practice, and future research.

Ethical Considerations

The researchers acknowledged their role and potential biases, maintaining reflexivity throughout the study. Ethical guidelines were rigorously followed, including informed consent, confidentiality, and respectful treatment of participants. The study prioritized the well-being and dignity of all participants, contributing valuable insights to the field of narrative inquiry.

Results and Discussion

Participants' Profile

In this qualitative narrative study, the participants comprised a diverse cohort of international Filipino students, each offering unique insights into their experiences with online education and support services. The group included Ali, a resilient advocate for enhanced educational support from Saudi Arabia; Walter, an outstanding performer adapting to online learning in the United Arab Emirates; Aiko, a digital navigator managing her studies from Japan; Teyam, an advocate for inclusive online learning infrastructure in Uzbekistan; Annie, a dedicated student transitioning through evolving online platforms in Thailand; Celine, an adaptive learner navigating online education from Malaysia; and Braum, a tech-savvy student engaging with digital learning tools in Oman. Their varied backgrounds and experiences provided a rich tapestry of perspectives, shedding light on the challenges and opportunities inherent in supporting international online learners.

Ali, a 17-year-old Filipino female, had resided in Saudi Arabia for her entire life. Enrolled in Grade 11-STEM-1P at New Era University Integrated School (NEUIS), she had previously attended the International Philippine School in Al-Khobar. With five years of online learning experience, Ali preferred interactive learning styles but faced challenges with limited utilization of educational support services at NEUIS due to counselor availability. Her stable internet access and diverse technological tools facilitated her online education, though she encountered cultural adaptation issues in Saudi Arabia. Ali chose NEUIS for its affordability and aspired to high-level education.

Walter, a 17-year-old Filipino male, had lived in the United Arab Emirates for just one year before being enrolled at NEUIS. With a strong academic record and involvement in various competitions, he seamlessly transitioned to online learning, despite having no prior experience. Walter had a stable internet connection and used a laptop and smartphone for his studies. He expressed a desire for more

personalized guidance and support services but had limited awareness of their availability. His goals included achieving high grades to secure admission to prestigious universities.

Aiko, a 16-year-old Filipino female, had lived in Japan for four years before studying online at NEUIS. Having been enrolled for six years, Aiko preferred a mix of synchronous and asynchronous learning and managed her online education effectively with a stable internet connection and various devices. Despite being aware of counseling services, she had not utilized them extensively. Aiko faced challenges with Japanese language communication but remained focused on college readiness and managing stress and time effectively.

Teyam, a 17-year-old Filipino female, had lived in Uzbekistan for five years and was enrolled in Grade 12 STEM 1P at NEUIS. Her extensive online learning experience led her to favor visual and interactive learning styles, and she utilized multiple technological platforms for her education. Although Teyam was aware of NEUIS's educational support services, she had not fully utilized them and had a moderate level of satisfaction with the services accessed. Her goals included maintaining academic excellence and improving time management skills.

Annie, a 16-year-old Filipino female, had resided in Thailand for a decade and had been with NEUIS since Grade 1. Her online learning experience had been mixed, with challenges in adapting to the evolving online education infrastructure. Annie preferred visual learning and group studying, using various online tools with a stable internet connection. She had not extensively utilized the educational support services at NEUIS and expressed a need for a more engaging and open study environment. Her goals included excelling academically and securing college admission.

Celine, a 16-year-old Filipino female, had lived in Malaysia for over five years while studying online at NEUIS. With a strong academic record, she had become adept at using interactive learning platforms and had stable internet access. Although Celine had occasionally utilized NEUIS's support services, she expressed a desire for more personalized assistance to improve her understanding of subjects. Her goals were to acquire essential skills for her future career and maintain good grades.

Braum, a 16-year-old Filipino male, had been living in Oman and studying online at NEUIS for over three years. His tech-savvy approach was reflected in his use of various online platforms and stable internet connection. Despite limited awareness of NEUIS's educational support services, Braum was generally satisfied with the support he received. His main goals were to complete high school and attend college, and he sought to learn more about available support services to enhance his educational experience.

The rise of online learning platforms brought significant changes to education. Institutions tried to adapt to the evolving needs of students, making it crucial to understand the experiences of those navigating this digital landscape. The stories of international Filipino students living outside the Philippines provided valuable insights into the challenges and opportunities within educational support services. These narratives helped to understand the factors influencing their choices, the services they used, the obstacles they faced, and their suggestions for improvement. The discussion and presentation focused on these experiences, drawing lessons to guide future conversations about educational support in the digital age. The findings and discussion were organized based on the research questions from the study.

Research Question 1: What are the narrative portraits of international online Filipino students?

The narrative portraits of international online Filipino students presented a complex view of their educational experiences. Key themes included Personal Background and Learning Environment, Psychological Factors and Academic Resilience, and Educational Processes and Problem-Solving. Participants' stories highlighted the impact of their cultural backgrounds and life circumstances on their education. For instance, Braum's experiences in Oman and Teyam's relocation journey from the Philippines to Bahrain and then Uzbekistan illustrated their diverse backgrounds. They also shared how they managed challenges like adapting to online learning, maintaining motivation, and overcoming obstacles.

Themes of resilience and adaptability were evident, with participants showing a strong ability to navigate transitions and solve problems. Their experiences underscored the importance of effective support structures and innovations in online education. The findings reveal that while students faced significant challenges, they also displayed remarkable perseverance and resourcefulness in their educational journeys.

Research Question 2: Why do the participants choose to be online learners?

Participants chose online learning for several reasons, primarily related to flexibility, accessibility, and personal circumstances. Key themes included Personal Factors Influencing the Choice of Online Schooling and Choosing Based on Educational Values and Goals. Many cited the flexibility of online education as a significant advantage, allowing them to manage their schedules and access learning from any location. For example, Celine transitioned to online learning due to her family's relocation to Malaysia, and Annie's family opted for online schooling to accommodate their nomadic lifestyle.

Pandemic-related challenges also influenced their decision, as the shift to online learning became essential during school closures. Family circumstances, such as relocation or parental decisions, played a crucial role in the choice to pursue online education. Participants also appreciated the comfort and familiarity of online environments, which helped them feel less nervous compared to traditional classrooms.

Moreover, participants valued online learning for its innovative approaches and quality education, often citing lower tuition fees and the opportunity to access specialized courses as key factors. Financial considerations, such as the high costs of traditional education, further made online learning a more viable option. Overall, the participants' choices were driven by a blend of practical needs, personal preferences, and the educational benefits offered by online learning platforms.

Research Question 3: What are the educational services the participants experienced as online learners?

Participants experienced various educational services through their online learning platforms, encompassing Learning Resources and Support Services, NEUVLE Integration, and Personalized Learning Experience. These services included access to online libraries, virtual guidance, structured learning materials, and interactive teaching methods.

Learning Resources and Support Services: Participants valued the availability of extensive online resources, including libraries, structured materials, and technical support. They noted the importance of virtual guidance, online assessments, and supplemental resources. However, challenges such as technical issues and feelings of isolation were also reported, with suggestions for improvements in mental health support and interactive tools.

Access to Resources and Materials: Participants appreciated the flexibility and convenience of accessing online libraries and structured learning materials. This access allowed them to manage their study sessions around personal commitments and engage with educational tools and platforms from anywhere.

Support Services: Key support services included virtual guidance, technical assistance, and peer collaboration. Participants valued teacher support, peer interactions, and tutoring, though some noted limitations in personalized assistance.

Communication and Collaboration: Participants highlighted the importance of communication channels and virtual classes, which facilitated real-time interactions with instructors and peers. Engagement in club activities and webinars also contributed to their academic and social development.

NEUVLE Integration and Online Learning Experience: The NEUVLE (New Era University Virtual Learning Environment) was praised for its well-organized learning guides, interactive features, and continuous teacher support. Participants found NEUVLE effective for curriculum delivery, assessment, and feedback.

Assessment and Feedback: Participants engaged in various online assessments and valued detailed feedback from teachers, which guided their learning and highlighted areas for improvement.

Personalized Learning Experience: Participants experienced tailored support through personalized learning materials and one-on-one tutoring. There were also calls for more mental health support and counseling to address stress and enhance overall well-being.

Research Question 4: What are the online students' challenges for which the participants believe they need educational support services?

Online students encounter several challenges, including Learning Environment Challenges and Motivational and Self-Management Challenges. Key issues include limited interaction with teachers, self-motivation struggles, time management difficulties, and connectivity problems. Research highlights that these difficulties impact students' academic success and overall experience (He et al., 2019; Ferri et al., 2020; Dhawan, 2020; Asad et al., 2023).

Learning Environment Challenges: Students face obstacles such as technical issues and communication difficulties. Problems with connectivity and accessing educational materials disrupt learning. Aiko experienced challenges with weak internet connections in the Philippines and noted the importance of reliable technical support. Braum faced issues with overloaded institutional email accounts and limited module support. Ali struggled with submitting files due to geographical constraints. These challenges necessitate improved technical assistance and communication channels.

Technical Issues: Participants reported connectivity problems and difficulties accessing or submitting materials, affecting their engagement and causing frustration. There is a clear need for enhanced technical support and more reliable internet connections.

Communication Challenges: Participants struggled with limited interaction with teachers, miscommunication, and lack of personal interaction. They faced difficulties in asking questions and obtaining timely responses from teachers, which hindered their learning. These challenges highlight the need for more effective communication channels and support for student engagement.

Motivational and Self-Management Challenges: Students also grapple with maintaining motivation and managing their time effectively. Braum noted a lack of motivation and engagement, while Walter experienced feelings of isolation and lack of support. Teyam emphasized the need for self-discipline and dedication. Challenges in maintaining motivation, managing schedules, and self-directed learning require educational support services that foster motivation, build self-management skills, and provide strategies for effective time management.

Motivational Challenges: Students experienced issues such as fluctuating motivation, feelings of isolation, and difficulties maintaining focus. The instability in learning environments and absence of face-to-face interactions contributed to these challenges.

Self-Management Challenges: Participants struggled with organizing study schedules, managing time effectively, and accessing educational resources. The lack of structured class times and face-to-face guidance made self-management particularly challenging.

Research Question 5: What suggestions may be made to enhance the educational support services provided to online learners based on the gathered narrative of this study?

Recommendations to enhance educational support services for online learners include improving the Learning Environment, Personalizing the Learning Experience, and Facilitating Collaborative Learning. These suggestions focus on strengthening technical support, enhancing communication, integrating multimedia resources, and supporting peer collaboration, aligned with the literature on effective online education practices (Bennet et al., 2020; Dhawan, 2020; Chung, 2023; Asad et al., 2023).

Enhancing the Learning Environment: Participants stressed the need for improved technical support and infrastructure. Recommendations include investing in technology upgrades, ensuring reliable connectivity, and enhancing technical support to address issues such as connectivity problems and software glitches. Suggestions also include creating structured remedial support sessions and integrating multimedia resources within learning platforms to improve engagement and comprehension.

Technical Support and Infrastructure Enhancement: Robust technical support systems and infrastructure improvements are crucial. Participants highlighted challenges with connectivity and device compatibility, recommending investments in hardware, software, and responsive technical support services to enhance the online learning experience.

Communication and Interaction Improvement: Participants identified the need for better communication channels and increased interaction opportunities. Enhancements such as chat forums, discussion boards, and virtual office hours were suggested to facilitate more effective communication and engagement between students and teachers. Ensuring consistent teacher availability and improving response times can also support better learning outcomes.

Multimedia Integration and Resource Utilization: Integrating multimedia resources like videos and interactive presentations into online courses can enhance engagement and understanding. Participants recommended using multimedia to cater to various learning styles and provide dynamic learning experiences.

Personalized Learning Experience: Personalized support services such as mentoring, tutoring, and flexible deadlines were emphasized as key to improving the online learning experience. Providing academic and mental health support, along with accommodating diverse schedules and individual needs, can help students manage their studies more effectively.

Facilitating Collaborative Learning: Encouraging peer collaboration through group activities and discussion forums was highlighted. Establishing peer networks and support sessions can enhance student interaction and create a sense of community. Additionally, legalizing group chats and streamlining administrative processes to support collaborative learning were suggested.

Administrative Efficiency: Streamlining administrative processes, including setting clear deadlines with flexibility, can improve the online learning experience. Legalizing group chat platforms for real-time communication and collaboration can further support student engagement and peer support.

Conclusions

The participants transitioned from various educational backgrounds, including traditional schooling and homeschooling, to online platforms. Their unique experiences shaped their approach to online learning.

Participants chose online education for reasons such as family circumstances, financial constraints, and the desire for personalized learning. Some sought flexibility, affordability, or a refuge from toxic environments.

The students had access to platforms like NEUVLE, virtual teacher meetings, and self-directed learning resources. Despite initial challenges, they benefited from structured materials and personalized support.

Challenges included internet connectivity issues, time zone differences, language barriers, and cultural adaptation difficulties, all of which impacted their engagement and academic success.

Based on their experiences, participants suggested improvements in communication, administrative processes, personalized learning materials, social support networks, and cultural inclusivity. They also advocated for greater flexibility, accessibility, and technological support.

Future research should consider conducting longitudinal studies to assess the long-term impact of online education on the academic performance, career trajectories, and personal growth of international online Filipino students. By tracking students over an extended period, researchers can gain insights into the factors that influence their success and well-being in online learning environments. Such studies could also explore how students' experiences and needs evolve over time, offering valuable information for educational institutions and policymakers.

Comparative studies could be valuable in understanding the experiences of international online Filipino students by contrasting them

with other student populations. This approach could reveal similarities, differences, and best practices in online education. By examining students from various cultural backgrounds, linguistic abilities, and geographic locations, researchers may gain a deeper understanding of the factors influencing student engagement, satisfaction, and academic performance in online learning settings. Additionally, these studies could evaluate the effectiveness of different support services and instructional strategies in meeting the diverse needs of students.

Intervention studies are recommended to assess the effectiveness of specific support services and interventions aimed at addressing the challenges faced by international online Filipino students. By implementing targeted interventions and evaluating their impact on student outcomes, researchers can identify promising practices and strategies to enhance the educational experience of this population. Areas of focus could include language support, cultural adaptation, technology integration, and academic mentoring, providing evidence-based recommendations for educators and policymakers.

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Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Signor Rinno D. Montales, PhD
New Era University – Philippines

Luningning B. De Castro, PhD

New Era University – Philippines

Luzale D. Henson, PhD

New Era University – Philippines

Ronnie G. Cainglet, EdD

New Era University – Philippines

Niclie L. Tiratira, PhD

New Era University – Philippines

Ligaya Z. Del Rosario, PhD

New Era University – Philippines

Vivian I. Buhain, EdD

New Era University – Philippines